

JOB SATISFACTION AS A CONTRIBUTING FACTOR OF EDUCATORS PERFORMANCES

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Abstract:

This study aims to see and know picture of job satisfaction, picture of the performance of the educators, and what is the contribution of job satisfaction to the performance of the educators in Sanggar Kegiatan Belajar (SKB), learning activity studios. Therefore, research using correlational research designs with the entire educators population in the Learning Activity Studios of West Sumatra. Therefore, studies using correlational research designs with populations of all educators at Learning Activity Studios (SKB) West Sumatra. The findings of the research indicate (1) Job satisfaction of educators of Learning Activity Studios in West Sumatra are still in low category; (2) The performance of Educators of Learning Activity Studios (SKB) in West Sumatra is still in the low category; and (3) Job satisfaction has a significant contribution to the performance of educators of Learning Activity Studios (SKB). Therefore, it is suggested to policy makers, especially leaders of Learning Activity Studios (SKB) institutions to provide encouragement, both morally and materially to improve job satisfaction of educators.

Keywords: job satisfaction, educators' performance

1. Introduction

Educators are those who have an important role in achieving nonformal education success. This is related to the main tasks of educators as educators with the main task of teaching and learning activities, program assessment, and the development of Nonformal and Informal Education (PNFI) model in Technical Implementation Unit (UPT)/Regional Technical Implementation Unit (UPTD) and PNFI Unit (Menteri Negara Pendayagunaan Aparatur Negara dan Reformasi Birokrasi Republik Indonesia, *Jabatan Fungsional Penilik dan Angka Kredit*). Therefore, the success of the educators in carrying

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out its duties as an educator will determine the success of its students learning in out of school education/ordinary non-formal.

The success of educators will be seen through the performance of educators. Performance or work performance is the execution of functions demanded of a person, performance is an act, an achievement, or a general exhibition of skills (Whitmore et al.). However, in reality, there are still many educators who have not shown the performance as expected. According to Kopelman, Brief, & Guzzo (1990), the factors that affect performance are individual characteristics, organizational characteristics, and work characteristics. Furthermore, Kopelman et al., (1990) explained that performance other than influenced by environmental factors, also highly dependent of individual characteristics such as ability, knowledge, skills, motivation, norms, and values. Educators performance allegedly influenced by several factors, among them is job satisfaction (Riza et al.).

Job satisfaction is one of the important means of human resource in management of an organization/institution. Job satisfaction is essentially one of the psychological aspects that reflect a person's feelings toward his work, he will feel satisfied with the suitability between his ability, his skills and his expectations with the work he faces.

Satisfaction is actually a subjective condition which is the result of a conclusion based on a comparison of what a person receives from his job as expected or desired and thought of as appropriate or entitled to it (Martoyo). So it can be concluded sketchily that job satisfaction is a person's feelings towards his work (Tutuncu and Kozak). This means that the conception of job satisfaction is seen as the result of human interaction with the work environment. In addition, a person's sense of work is at the same time a reflection of his attitude to work. Job satisfaction is the employee's satisfaction with his job between what the employee expect from his job/office (Davis and Newstrom).

Meanwhile Robbins (1994) said job satisfaction is as an individual's general attitude towards his work. Work demands interaction with colleagues, employers, organizational rules and policies, performance standards, working conditions and so on. A person with a high level of job satisfaction shows a positive attitude towards the work, otherwise a person is not satisfied with his work showing a negative attitude towards the work (Khan et al.; Robbins). Based on this description can be concluded that job satisfaction perceived by educators will affect its performance as an educator in Learning Activity Studios (SKB) West Sumatra.

Based on the background of the proposed problem, the purpose of this discussion is to look at (1) To see an overview educators of Learning Activity Studios (SKB) job satisfaction; (2) To see an overview educators of Learning Activity Studios (SKB) performance; (3) Is there a relationship between job satisfaction with performance of educators of Learning Activity Studios (SKB); And (4) How much contribution of job satisfaction to educators in Learning Activity Studios (SKB) performance.

2. Method

The study was designed using correlational research design. The correlational design explains that in addition to describing the actual phenomena of the variables studied, it also reveals the presence or absence of a relationship between the independent variable (predictor) of job satisfaction (X) with the dependent variable (criterion) ie the performance of educators (Y), as well as finding the amount of independent variable contribution to the dependent.

The population of this study was all educators at Learning Activity Studios (SKB) West Sumatra. The sampling technique used is stratified random sampling technique, random sampling with stratification can be used if the population element has heterogeneous characteristic, and the heterogeneity has significant meaning on the achievement of research objectives, the researcher can take samples in this way (Sugiyono). In this case because educators have the heterogeneity of educators stratas, i.e. First Educators, Young Educators, and Madya Educators (Menteri Negara Pendayagunaan Aparatur Negara dan Reformasi Birokrasi Republik Indonesia, *Jabatan Fungsional Pamong Belajar Dan Angka Kredit*).

Instrument used to collect data on job satisfaction (X) and educators performance (Y), questionnaire using Likert scale measurement model with range of 4, with alternative answer Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

To test the accuracy and reliability of the instruments used experiments conducted on educators who are not used as research samples. Furthermore, the test results of the instrument are analyzed by testing in the form of (a) validity test and (b) reliability test. To test the validity of points, the instrument tested the subject of research that did not become the sample of this study. The data obtained through the experiments were empirically analyzed by correlating the points scores and the total score by using the Pearson Product Moment correlation technique (Hatch and Farhady). The reliability or consistency test of the instrument or measurement tool uses consistency test items, which is the consistency of the respondent's answer on an item in the size of the Alpha coefficient (Cronbach; Ary et al.).

If the Alpha coefficient shows ≥ 0.70 , then it can be said that the items in the questionnaire are reliable (Ardhana; Hair et al.; Uyanto).

The analysis technique used is simple regression technique. Simple regression analysis technique is an analytical technique used to analyze the relationship and see the contribution of one dependent variable and one independent variable (Hair et al.). To that end, computer assistance with Statistic Package for Social Sciencies (SPSS) for Window Release 17.0 was used.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Result

A. An Overview of Job Satisfaction of Educators at Learning Activity Studios (SKB) West Sumatra

Based on the results of data analysis using the percentage formula illustrated the performance of educators seen in table 1.

Table 1: An Overview of Job Satisfaction of Educators at Learning Activity Studios (SKB) West Sumatra

Interval	Score	Category	Frequency Percentage
65 - 80	Very High	7	18
49 - 64	High	11	29
33 - 48	Low	15	39
17 - 32	Very Low	5	13
Total		38	100

Based on table 1, it is illustrated that the level of job satisfaction of Learning Activity Studios (SKB) educators in West Sumatera is still in the lower category. This is reflected from the most frequent scores obtained by respondents is in the range 33-48 (low criteria). This means that of the 38 people educators, so as many as 15 people (39%) get a score on the range 33-48 interval scores (which is in the low category). For more details, the picture can be seen in the following histogram.

Figure 1: Histogram Educators Job Satisfaction

B. Overview of Educators Performance in Learning Activity Studios (SKB) West Sumatera

Based on the results of data analysis using the formula percentage illustrated that the performance can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Overview of Educators Performance in Learning Activity Studios (SKB) West Sumatera

Interval	Score	Category	Frequency Percentage
65 - 80	Very High	7	18
49 - 64	High	10	27
33 - 48	Low	15	39
17 - 32	Very Low	6	16
Total		38	100

Based on table 2 it is illustrated that the level of performance of educators Learning Activity Studios (SKB) West Sumatra is still in the low category. This is reflected from the most frequent scores obtained by respondents is in the range 33 - 48 (low criteria). That is, from 38 people educators, then as many as 14 people (37%) obtained a score on a range of 33-48 score intervals (which included in the low category). For more details the picture can be seen in the following histogram 2 following.

3.2 Hypothesis Test Results

In this section, prior to the data analysis, the results of simple regression principle test put forward first. Before the data is analyzed by using simple regression analysis technique, the assumption test is used as a requirement in simple regression analysis technique. According to Sudarmanto (2005) the tests are normality test, linearity test, homogeneity test, multicollinearity test, autocorrelation test, and heteroscedasticity test. Each is described as follows.

Normality tests are performed to determine whether the distribution of data follows or approaches the normal distribution. Because, good data is data that has a normal distribution pattern or close to normal. Based on the normality test, when viewed from the distribution of data on the QQ plot then the data clustered on the test line and leads to the top right. Accordingly, a reasonable regression is used to analyze the data.

Homogeneity test is done to detect the presence or absence of homogeneity, used to see the spread of points (dots) on the graph. If the points spread and do not form a certain pattern, then it is said the data is homogeneous (Santoso). When viewed from the graph generated random points found, it can be concluded that the distribution of data homogeneous. Thus, the analysis is worth continuing.

Linearity test is done in pairs between each independent variable with the dependent variable. In this case will be seen the linearity of the relationship between independent variable achievement motivation and dependent variable job preparedness. The linearity test is performed by performing 'compare means' analysis by comparing the significance value with the selected alpha level (here 5%). The data say linear because it is significant for 'deviation from the linearity' > of the alpha set.

Based on the results of data analysis of 'scatter plot', seen regression line on the graph of each variable pointing to the top right. Thus, it can be concluded that the relationship between the dependent variable with the independent variable is linear. Therefore, regression analysis can be used.

A. Correlation between Job Satisfaction and Educators Performance

The first hypothesis, formulated in the form of working hypothesis (Ha) which reads, "There is a significant relationship between job satisfaction with the performance of educators of Learning Activity Studios (SKB) In West Sumatra". To test this hypothesis, Pearson correlation (r) was used. The results of correlation analysis (r) obtained is 0.794 with a significant level of 0.000 or smaller than the tolerance given 0.05. Based on such calculations, the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected. It can be said that job satisfaction has a significant relationship with the performance of educators. This means that if the work satisfaction of educators will be enhanced will be followed by increased performance of educators or vice versa. As for the picture of the correlation coefficient, the probability can be seen in table 3 below.

Table 3: Summary of Independent Variables Correlation Coefficient with Dependent Variables

Variable	Coefficient Correlation (R)	Probability	Information
X → Y	0,856	0,000	Significant Relationship

(X) = Job Satisfaction

(Y) = Performance

B. Contribution of Job Satisfaction to Educator's Performance

Contribution Job satisfaction (X) on educators performance (Y). To see the contribution of independent variable of job satisfaction (X) to performance (Y) will be seen from the value of R Square in Summary Model table. To test the amount of contribution is used R Square value (Sudarmanto). From Summary Model table found the magnitude of R Square value is 0,725 with significance 0.000. This means that the independent variable of job satisfaction (X) gives a significant contribution of 0, 765 (76.5%) on the performance of educators.

Table x: xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.875 ^a	.765	.758	7.85078

a. Predictors: (Constant), job satisfaction

b. Dependent Variable: performance

C. Test of Regression Equation Coefficients

For the purposes of test coefficient of regression equation can be seen on the result of regression analysis depicted in table 4.5. In table 4.5 test table of regression coefficient constant 3,975 coefficient of Work Satisfaction (X) 0,907, Therefore, model of regression equation is $Y = 3,975 + 0,907 X$. For more details can be seen table 4.

Table 4: Test Results of Coefficient of Regression Equation

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.975	4.634		.858	.397
	Job satisfaction	.907	.091	.856	9.920	.000

a. Dependent Variable: job satisfaction (X)

b. Dependent Variable performance (Y)

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be drawn some conclusions, as follows.

- The research findings indicate that the level of job satisfaction of Learning Activity Studios (SKB) educators in West Sumatra is still in the lower category. The low level of job satisfaction is marked by many educators who have not been satisfied with career development opportunities, they have not felt comfortable in the work environment and have not felt comfortable with the social conditions in their institutions.
- Level of performance Learning Activity Studios (SKB) educators in West Sumatra is still in the low category. This means that there are still many educators who have not shown the maximum performance, such as reluctant to do the task, did not complete the task in accordance with the time given, and did not take the initiative to find solutions to the difficulty of the task.
- Job satisfaction has a significant relationship with the performance of Learning Activity Studios (SKB) educators, this is evident from the magnitude of the correlation (r) and the magnitude of the significance price (sig) found. That is, if job satisfaction is improved then the performance of educators will be better or otherwise if job satisfaction decreases then the educator's performance will decrease.
- Job satisfaction has a significant contribution to the performance of Learning Activity Studios (SKB) educators. That is, increased or decreased performance of Learning Activity Studios (SKB) educators predicted by increased or decreased job satisfaction. So to improve the educator's performance, it is necessary to improve the job satisfaction of the educator first.

4.2 Recommendation

Following up the research findings that illustrate that the low level of job satisfaction that contribute significantly to the low performance of educators, it is advisable to the leaders of institutions, educator coordinators, authorized officials, and academic staffs to provide inputs and guidance, to improve job satisfaction of educators. Job satisfaction of educators will in turn have an impact on performance improvement, through actions that can create an atmosphere that makes educators feel satisfaction in

working at Learning Activity Studios (SKB). Job satisfaction can be grown and developed by providing opportunities for advancement, providing job security, providing stable work situations and conditions. Furthermore, good supervision, providing good place conditions, maintaining a social relationship, and smooth communication can also foster optimal job satisfaction.

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